

Demonstrative process for the production and enzymatic recycling of environmentally safe, superior and versatile PHA-based rigid packaging solutions by plasma integration in the value chain

The Challenges

The increasing use of bioplastics in the packaging sector is driven by the continuous demand for sustainable products by consumers and brands alike due to a growing awareness of the environmental impact and the need to reduce the dependency on fossil resources. The bioplastics industry's continuous innovations make the number of manufacturers, converters and end-users increase steadily. New and innovative biopolymers such as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) show a very high relative growth rate.

New ways of producing PHAs are of great importance, being one of the challenges open to sourcing it from 2nd-3rd generation raw materials instead of raw sugars.

The use of by-products for PHA production has yet to reach an industrial level of market potential. BioSupPack focuses on brewer's spent grains (BSG), the most abundant by-product from the brewery industry, available at low or no cost and produced in large quantities, to produce PHA formulations.

The Approach

The project delivers versatile and competitive bio-based packaging solutions based on PHA suitable for food and beverages, but also for cosmetics and homecare. It also aims to establish a new value chain, including the development of logistics and management of both brewery and packaging waste. BioSupPack upscales the production of **novel rigid packaging products** using new PHA-based polymers with improved properties. These products will have different formats such as **bottles, trays, bowls, coffee cups, and secondary packaging for glass bottles etc.**

BioSupPack enhances the brewer's spent grain (BSG) to sugar conversion yield to more than 70% of the theoretical yield. It scales up air plasma treatment technologies for BSG pretreatment. BioSupPack develops efficient fermentations for PHB production and it scales up an enzymatic bioprocess for recycling 3HB monomers from PHB-based used packages.

Expected Outputs

Processes

- Upscaling of the production of new PHA-based products to a demonstration level.
- Integration of the plasma technology throughout the value chain for the pre-treatment of brew spent grains, packaging treatment and finally, for the pre-treatment of packaging waste.
- Development of a system capable of identifying and sorting of the BioSupPack waste (>90% of BioSupPack materials identified).
- Creation of a new value chain by managing both brewery and packaging waste flows.
- Sustainability and compliance with the European standards and legislation.
- Maximization of the impact after the end of the project by exploiting results.

Demonstrators

- Crafting of highly performing PHA-based rigid packaging with properties similar to those of conventional petrochemical plastics in the market, increasing the use of renewable resources (brewer's spent grains) for PHA formulations up to >85%.
- The recyclability of the novel BioSupPack products (designed to be recycled): Mechanical and enzymatic recycling processes to reintroduce materials in the production step and/or recover carbon sources for the fermentation process (>30% carbon source supply).
- Demonstration of the end-users' validation and acceptance of the novel BioSupPack products.

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Bio-based Industries Consortium

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